

Deliverable D-JRP22-WP5.7

Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: ANSES, FLI, RIVM, PIWET, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, UT, BIOR, CVRL, IZSS, UNF, UH, IP, LRUJ, NPI, SDAS, COMSATS, VTL

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP22-WP5.7
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Other contributors	All participants
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

FINAL MEETING OF MEME (Rome, 22-23 November)

Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain

MEME final meeting; 22-23 November 2022

AGENDA: DAY 1 (22/11/2022)

12:30-13:00 Registration (MEME participants)

13:00-14:00 Lunch

14:00-14:05 Welcome Casulli (Project Coordinator, ISS)

14:05-14:30 MEME project: aims, overview, achievements (Casulli, ISS)

WP2: VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS

14:30-14:40 WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay (Davidson, NVI)

14:40-14:50 WP2-T3. **New.** Comparison of Magnetic Capture protocols for extraction and detection of Em DNA in feces (Maksimov, FLI)

WP3: DEVELOPMENT of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS

WP3-T1. New molecular markers for Em and Eg sl: from rapid diagnostics to source attribution

14:50-15:00 WP3-T1-ST2. New microsatellite markers (Umhang, ANSES)

WP3-T2. New molecular methods for the detection of Em and Eg

15:00-15:10 WP3-T2-ST2. **New.** New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Eg sl and Em (Maksimov, FLI)

15:10-15:20 WP3-T2-ST4. **New.** New rapid molecular identification of Em and Eg sl tissue samples by novel PCR-RFLP (Umhang, ANSES)

WP3-T3. Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using Regions Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS

15:20-15:30 WP3-T3-ST1. Challenges with nanopore sequencing for sequence identification of Eg/Em RSE samples (Øines, NVI)

15:30-16:00 Coffee break

16:10-16:20 WP3-T3-ST2. **New.** Detection of the mitogenome of Em by RSE method and Illumina-NGS (Maksimov, FLI)

16:20-16:35 WP3-T5. Comparison of existing and new techniques for molecular diagnostic of Em and Eg sl (Umhang, ANSES)

16:35-16:55 WP3-T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg (Umhang, ANSES)

WP3-T6-ST1. Contamination of lettuces

WP3-T6-ST2. **New.** Contamination of berries

WP3-T6-ST3. **New.** Dispersion of Em/Eg eggs in the soil

16:55-17:05 WP3-T7. Prevalence of Em/Eg in dogs (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas (Karamon, PIWET)

20:00 **Social dinner:** *Roman cuisine in San Lorenzo* (ISS) (appointment at 19:30 at Best Wester Globus Hotel)

AGENDA: DAY 2 (23/11/2022)

WP3: DEVELOPMENT of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS

WP3-T8. **New.** Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE/AE

9:00-9:20 WP3-T8-ST2. **New.** Unveiling the impact of human CE in Europe (1997-2021) (Casulli, ISS)

9:20-9:30 WP3-T8-ST4. **New.** Intestinal zoonotic parasites in dogs and foxes in an Em endemic area in Limburg (van der Giessen, RIVM)

WP4: TRAINING, DISSEMINATION & PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES

9:30-10:00 Consolidate WP4-T1. Trainings: M-PCRs (Maksimov, FLI); MC-RT-PCR (Davidson, NVI); RSE-NGS (Øines, NVI)

10:00-10:30 Consolidate WP4-T2. PTs: SSCT (Boue, ANSES); MC-RT-PCR (Davidson, NVI); RSE-NGS (Berg, SSI)

WP5: SCIENTIFIC AND ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT

WP5-T2. Administrative and scientific management

10:30-11:00 **The end of 3-year journey: consolidate the Final report** (Casulli, ISS)

11:00-11:30 **Coffee break**

11:30-13:00 **Roundtables on WPs, Tasks and Final Report** (all)

13:00-14:00 **Lunch**

14:00-15:00 **Roundtables on WPs, Tasks and Final Report** (all)

15:00-15:30 **Coffee break**

16:00 **Conclusions and adjourn**

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